

Effect of phosphorus with and without zinc on wetland rice

A. Buntan, L. Gunarto, M. Rauf, and I. T. Corpuz, Agronomy Department, Maros Research Institute for Food Crops, P.O. Box 173, Ujung Pandang, Indonesia

Data from the 1981 and 1982 dry season (DS), Long-Term Soil Fertility Trials at Lanrang Substation showed that application of Zn significantly decreased rice grain yields. Responses to phosphorus also were observed. We designed an experiment in the 1984-85 DS (Nov-Feb) to determine yield response of rice to different P rates, with and without Zn.

The clay loam soil had pH 5.9 (slightly acidic); 2.6% organic matter content (low); 9 ppm available P (medium); 13.8, 8.8, 0.8 meq exchangeable Ca, Mg, K/100 g soil (adequate).

P, N, and K were applied in the form

Response of IR54 to P with and without Zn. Lanrang, Indonesia, 1984-85 DS.

Treatment	Grain yield ^a	Straw yield
	(t/ha) at 14% moisture	(t/ha) (sun-dried)
Control	4.7	4.7
13 kg P	6.0	5.3
13 kg P + 5 kg ZnO	5.8	5.4
26 kg P	6.0	5.4
26 kg P + 5 kg ZnO	6.0	5.5
40 kg P	5.9	5.8
40 kg P + 5 kg ZnO	5.8	5.6
53 kg P	6.0	5.2
53 kg P + 5 kg ZnO	5.8	5.4
66 kg P	5.2	5.5
66 kg P + 5 kg ZnO	5.9	5.5
0 P + 100 kg N + 50 kg K + 5 kg ZnO	5.7	5.6
LSD (0.05)	0.7	0.8
(0.01)	0.8	0.9
CV (%)	9.5	8.4

^aBased on 25 hills free of rat damage (harvestable area = 4 m²).

of TSP, urea, and KCl, respectively; 100 kg N/ha and 50 kg P/ha were applied as basal. Treatments were arranged in a randomized complete block design with four replications (see table).

ZnO at 5 kg/ha with P rates ranging

from 13 kg P to 66 kg P/ha in 13-kg P increments did not significantly affect grain and straw yields of IR54. There were no significant differences between P with and without Zn. And there was no response to phosphorus. □

Response of spring rice to fertilizer practices in rice - rapeseed rotation

V. Prakash, V. K. Bhatnagar, and P. Singh, Vivekananda Parvatiya Krishi Anusandhan Shala, Almora 263601, Uttar Pradesh (U.P.), India

Spring rice, the principal crop in the midhills of U.P., is sown under rainfed conditions in Mar and harvested in Sep. A short-duration (Oct-Feb) rapeseed (*Brassica campestris* L. var. *toria*) was found to fit the intervening period best. But yields are low because farmers use very low amounts of chemical fertilizers (4-5 kg/ha). Farmyard manure (FYM) is the principal source of plant nutrients.

We studied the response of spring rice to N and FYM and the residual effect on a succeeding rapeseed crop at Hawalbagh, Almora (1,250 m above mean sea level, average annual rainfall 1,027.3 mm) for 3 yr (1983-86).

The soil was sandy loam (pH 6.2, 0.43% organic C, CEC 22 meq/100 g,

Effect of N and FYM applied to spring rice on grain yield of spring rice and rapeseed. Almora, India, 1983-86.

Manurial treatment		Yield (t/ha)							
		1983-84		1984-85		1985-86		Mean	
N rate (kg/ha)	FYM (t/ha)	Rice	Rapeseed	Rice	Rapeseed	Rice	Rapeseed	Rice	Rapeseed
0	0	1.43	0.22	1.41	0.22	0.79	0.30	1.21	0.24
0	10	1.72	0.31	1.81	0.32	1.66	0.51	1.73	0.38
0	20	1.91	0.37	2.07	0.43	1.93	0.61	1.97	0.47
20	0	1.50	0.19	1.60	0.22	0.95	0.32	1.35	0.24
20	10	1.81	0.38	1.91	0.33	1.77	0.53	1.83	0.41
20	20	2.02	0.37	2.26	0.44	2.28	0.62	2.19	0.48
LSD (0.05) N		0.10	ns	0.15	ns	0.15	ns		
FYM		0.16	0.06	0.13	0.08	0.15	0.03		
N×FYM		ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns		

22.7 kg available P (Bray's)/ha, 229.6 kg available K/ha). Two levels of N (0 and 20 kg N/ha) and three levels of FYM (0, 10, and 20 t/ha) were applied only to spring rice, in a factorial randomized block design with three replications. FYM applied the first yr had 0.65% N, 0.23% P, 0.60% K, and 18.8% moisture content; in the second yr, it had 0.61% N, 0.27% P, 0.58% K, and 16.7%

moisture content; and in the third year it had 0.56% N, 0.21% P, 0.65% K, and 15.5% moisture content. Rice variety VL 206 was seeded the second half of Mar and harvested the middle of Sep. Rapeseed variety T9 was planted the beginning of Oct and harvested in the second half of Feb.

Rice yield increased by 0.14 t/ha with 20 kg N/ha (see table). Yield increases

with 10 and 20 t FYM/ha were 0.52 and 0.76 t/ha, respectively. Highest yield was with 20 t FYM and 20 kg N/ha.

The residual effect of FYM on the following rapeseed crop was significant.

Rapeseed yields were 0.17 and 0.24 t/ha higher with 10 and 20 t FYM/ha, respectively. The residual effect of fertilizer N on rapeseed yield was not significant.

Applying 20 kg N with 20 t FYM/ha to spring rice not only increased rice yield, but also doubled yield of the succeeding rapeseed crop. □

Disease management

Field evaluation of fungicides to control rice sheath blight (ShB)

Y. Suryadi and T. S. Kadir, Sukamandi Research Institute for Food Crops, West Java, Indonesia

We tested eight fungicides against *Rhizoctonia solani* in the field.

Pelita I-2 was planted in a randomized block design with three replications in 4- × 5-m plots at 20- × 20-cm spacing. Plants were artificially inoculated 55 d after transplanting (DT) by placing small amounts of ShB inoculum on rice husk at the center of each hill. Fungicides were sprayed at 60, 67, and 74 DT, and disease incidence (lesion length and relative lesion height)

Control of rice ShB by fungicides. Sukamandi, Indonesia, 1986-87.^a

Treatment	Application rate (formulation/ha)	Plant height (cm)	Lesion length (cm)	RLN ^b (%)	Severity ^c (%)
Benomyl	0.25 kg	124.16 a	58.26 cde	46.94 bc	39.14 cd
Mancozeb	2.0 kg	125.16 a	49.08 abcd	39.21 ab	26.37 abc
PCNB	1.0 kg	123.59 a	52.89 bcd	42.72 abc	35.60 bcd
Chlorothalonil	1.7 kg	125.34 a	46.06 ab	36.77 ab	22.12 ab
Carbendazim	0.8 kg	125.91 a	56.07 bcde	44.52 abc	33.53 bcd
Triazole	0.5 liter	116.77 b	40.13 a	34.16 a	19.5 a
Captafol	1.5 liter	123.51 ab	59.23 c	46.14 bc	39.74 cd
Maneb + zineb	1.0 kg	121.6 ab	47.69 abc	39.15 ab	26.30 abc
Control (unsprayed)	—	126.69 a	65.78 e	51.92 c	48.8 d
CV (%)		3.01	11.29	11.07	14.41

^aMean of 3 replications. Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bRLH = $\frac{\text{lesion length}}{\text{plant height}} \times 100$

^cSeverity = $\frac{0 (n_0) + 1 (n_1) + 5 (n_3) + 20 (n_5) + 50 (n_7) + 100 (n_9)}{\text{number of tillers observed}} \times 100$

n0 - n9 = number of tillers with 0-9 scale.

measured 25 d after flowering.

Triazole was most effective in inhibiting enlargement of ShB lesions. Significant lesion reduction also

occurred with chlorothalonil, mancozeb, and maneb + zineb treatments (see table). No phytotoxicity occurred in any treatment. □

Survival of rice root-knot nematode juveniles in moist soil

M. H. Soomro, Agriculture Department, University of Reading, Reading, United Kingdom (present address: Crop Diseases Research Institute, National Agricultural Research Centre, Park Road, Islamabad, Pakistan)

Severe infestations of the soil by *Meloidogyne graminicola* can cause up to 50% yield losses. To develop an efficient control method for this nematode we need to know its survival capacity in the absence of a host plant.

To measure rice root-knot nematode survival, eight plastic pots were filled with sterilized soil and inoculated with 4,000 freshly hatched *M. graminicola* juveniles/pot. The soil was kept moist. Pots were incubated at two

Nematodes surviving soil incubation and infesting host plant roots. Reading, UK.

Soil incubation period (mo)	Survival (no./g roots)	
	26±4°C	20±1°C
2	442	812
3	133	693
4	96	451
5	536	707

temperatures: four pots at 26 ± 4 °C, and four pots at 20 ± 1 °C.

Survival and viability of the nematodes were measured by a bioassay method at 2, 3, 4, and 5 mo after inoculation. After assay, a 2-wk-old seedling of *Echinochloa colona* was planted in one pot from each incubation temperature and kept at 26 ± 4 °C.

Seedlings were uprooted 2 mo after transplanting. Roots washed free from soil were weighed and fixed in FA 4:1.

Fixed roots were stained in acid fuchsin in lacto-glycerol and cleared for 24 h. Number of nematodes in the roots was estimated by counting nematodes in three 0.5-g subsamples (see table).

Second stage juvenile of rice root-knot nematodes can survive in soil without any host plant for up to 5 mo at temperatures up to 26°C and remain viable to invade host roots and reproduce. □

Recovery of rice tungro virus (RTV) from rice stubble

Z. M. Flores, E. R. Tiongco, R. C. Cabunagan, and H. Hibino, IRRI

Rice stubble can serve as a RTV source. In a greenhouse study, stubble of IR22 and IR36 naturally infected with both